

The Influence of Self-Efficacy and Entrepreneurial Skills Towards the Readiness of Entrepreneurial Students in the Era of Society 5.0

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine self-efficacy and entrepreneurial skills on student entrepreneurship readiness in the era of society 5.0 at STKIP Persada Khatulistiwa Sintang, and the effect of self-efficacy and entrepreneurial skills on student entrepreneurial readiness at STKIP Persada Khatulistiwa Sintang. The method used in this research is quantitative and the form of the research is multiple linear regression research. The population in this study were 329 students of STKIP Persada Khatulistiwa Sintang with a total sample of 76 students. Sampling technique with random sampling. The data collection technique used was a questionnaire. Data processing in research uses EXCEL and SPSS 26 with data processing techniques using validity tests, linearity tests, classical assumption tests, contribution tests and hypothesis testing. The results showed that self-efficacy and entrepreneurship skills partially had a significant influence on student entrepreneurship readiness. This was shown by the t_{count} self-efficacy (X_1) $0.000 < 0.05$ and t_{count} entrepreneurship skills (X_2) $0.000 < 0.05$. Self-efficacy and entrepreneurial skills simultaneously have a significant effect on student readiness for entrepreneurship, this is indicated by a sig value of $0.000 < \alpha$ sig level value of 0.05 and an F count of $170.065 > F_{\text{table}}$. Among the self-efficacy and entrepreneurship skills that have the most dominant influence on student entrepreneurship readiness is variable X_2 (entrepreneurship skills) because it has a higher coefficient of 0.616 compared to variable X_1 (self-efficacy) with a coefficient value of 0.294 . Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that Self-Efficacy and Entrepreneurial Skills affect the Entrepreneurial Readiness of Students in the Society 5.0 Era at STKIP Persada Khatulistiwa Sintang

INTRODUCTION

In the current era of globalization, competition and challenges are getting tougher, especially in the economic field which is not only competition at the local, regional and national levels, but also global competition from various countries that are ready to compete. In this era, entrepreneurs who are able to innovate and creativity are needed. However, the problem faced today is the number of workers who are growing rapidly and the number is high, this causes the availability of jobs is very limited so that it can cause unemployment. This will be related to other problems such as income inequality, poverty, slowing growth and the economy.

Based on Global Entrepreneurship Index data in 2019. Indonesia is ranked 74 out of 137 countries. Indonesia's index value of 21% is equivalent to developing countries in Landmark Asia, namely Vietnam, with an index value of 23.2%. Therefore, the government is currently drafting a presidential decree on national entrepreneurship development as well as part of the Job Creation Law and PP No. 7/2021, which will focus on creating new entrepreneurs. Through the creation of innovative young or mineral entrepreneurs can create quality jobs.

According to Rumawouw (Hapsah and Savira, 2015: 81), stating the presence of entrepreneurs can help a country's economic growth and by maximizing entrepreneurial potential, it will strengthen the economy because the entrepreneurial process creates added value and development in various aspects. The emergence and development of entrepreneurship will also develop employment for the community. The development of self-efficacy and entrepreneurial skills towards the readiness of entrepreneurial students is felt to have not been optimal.

Entrepreneurship is considered important in the development of the socio-economic welfare level of the community. This is because entrepreneurship is a major factor in economic development, and is considered a source of job creation, poverty alleviation, innovation and community development as well as economic competitiveness of Ahmed et al (Priandi, 2020: 234).

According to Davinci (Fauzia, 2022: 7), a person's readiness in entrepreneurship is not only seen from the material, but there are several other aspects such as interest, training, guidance, risk-taking attitudes, as well as a sense of confidence and confidence. According to Zebua (Fauzia, 2022: 13) readiness is the overall condition of a person to respond and practice an activity that contains mental aspects, skills and attitudes. Entrepreneurial readiness is the ability and willingness to prepare everything needed when you want to start entrepreneurship. To be able to have this ability, various abilities in the field of entrepreneurship are needed so that they are ready for entrepreneurship.

Entrepreneurial readiness is a condition in which individuals differ in mental and physical readiness to respond to changes in the world of entrepreneurship. Ratum Buysang and Rasyid, (Komalasari and Anafarhanah, 2022;322) Aspects that can strengthen readiness in entrepreneurship are knowledge, skills, and attitudes or abilities". Yuliani (Utami and Denmar 2020:

647) stated that "entrepreneurial readiness is defined as a condition where individuals have a feeling of readiness with the provision of abilities, willingness and desires they have to face various situations in entrepreneurship.

Srianggareni (Widyawati and Mujiati, 2020: 1119) explained that entrepreneurial self-efficacy is the self-confidence that a person has will provide success and create satisfaction in entrepreneurship. In addition, an entrepreneur must have entrepreneurial skills to prepare himself as an entrepreneur. Skills are the ability to use reason, thoughts, ideas, and creativity in doing work, becoming more meaningful so as to produce a value from the results of the work. Skills will be better if you are always trained to increase and add abilities so that you become an expert and master. Skills are one of the keys to successful entrepreneurship. Qurnia and Sawitri (2022: 249) stated that students as part of the millennial generation who are considered more familiar with digital technology as well as educated figures are agents of change (Agent of Change) which is expected to transform from what used to be just a person job seeker Become a job creator.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The era of society 5.0 demands qualified skills and competencies. Because in the era of integration of the use of technology and the internet that is so sophisticated and still demands changes in the behavior of the world of higher education and the industrial world. In higher education it self, it is very necessary to develop an entrepreneurial culture to encourage the creation of new young entrepreneurs by applying the entrepreneurial knowledge they get. To be an entrepreneur must be creative, innovative and productive. "In addition, they must also be confident, brave and optimistic to achieve goals or ideals, achieve and obtain benefits" Mahanani et al (Danang et al, 2020: 99)

METHODOLOGY

This research is quantitative research, a form of multiple regression research. According to Sugiyono (2017: 275), "regression analysis is used to predict how far the value of the dependent variable changes, if the value of the independent variable is manipulated or changed or increased". The population in this study is students of STKPI Persada Khatulistiwa batch 2921/2022 Sintang totaling 329 respondents.

The sampling technique used is random sampling. According to Arikunto (2014: 177), "Random sampling technique is taken in mixed studies, subjects are in the population so that all subjects are considered equal. ". According to Sugiyono, "random sampling is a sampling technique from the population carried out randomly without paying attention to the stara in the population". Sugiyono in Roscore (2018: 1330) "the feasible sample size in research is between 30 to 500". Based on this view, the consideration of sampling as much as 10% of the total population, namely 76 respondents.

The data collection techniques and instruments used are indirect communication techniques or questionnaires (questionnaires) and

documentation. Data analysis techniques in this study use various tests including validity tests, reliability tests, descriptive analysis, classical assumption tests, contribution tests, and hypothesis tests. The test was conducted using the help of EXCEL and SPSS 26.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data processing of the results of this study uses several tests including validity tests, reliability tests, classical assumption tests (normality tests, linearity tests, and multicollinearity tests), contribution tests (multiple correlation tests, correlation tests, multiple linear regression tests, determination coefficient tests), and hypothesis tests (t tests and F tests). Test the validity and reliability of the research instrument using a questionnaire or questionnaire containing 20 statement items on each variable conducted at STKIP Persada Khatulistiwa Sintang during the research trial gave the test results that the research instrument was valid. In addition, the test results also show that the research instrument used is reliable.

A normality test is a procedure used to determine whether data is normally or abnormally distributed in a study. The normality test was performed with the Kolmogorov smirnow test using SPSS 26. If the significance value > 0.05 , then the residual is normally distributed. The results of the normality test conducted on each research variable showed self-efficacy of 0.79, entrepreneurial skills of 0.157 and entrepreneurial student readiness of 0.08. Based on the test results, it is known that the significance value of each variable is greater than 0.05, so it is declared normally distributed.

According to Kasmadi and Sunariah (2016: 120), "The linearity test aims to find out whether three variables have a linear relationship or not". If the significance value > 0.05 , then the hypothesis stating that the linear model is accepted. The output result of the linearity test shows a deviation from linearity value of 0.607. The sig value is greater than 0.05 ($0.607 > 0.05$). This shows that the variables of Self-Efficacy and Entrepreneurial Skills on Student Readiness for Entrepreneurship have a linear relationship.

Multicollinearity is whether there is a correlation between independent variables in the regression model (Juliandi, Irfan and Munarung, 2015: 23). The decision-making criterion for the use of tolerance and VIF values is if the tolerance value > 0.10 or the VIF value < 10 then there is no multicollinearity among independent variables. Conversely, if the tolerance value ≤ 0.10 or the VIF value ≥ 10 , there is multicollinearity among independent variables (Hamid et al, 2019: 101). The results showed the output of the VIF value of the Self-Efficacy variable of 0.2.592 and the Entrepreneurial Skills variable of 0.2.592. Based on these results, it can be concluded that the VIF value of the variables Self-Efficacy and Entrepreneurial Skills < 10 , so it does not show any symptoms of multicollinearity.

Multiple regression analysis to determine whether or not there is an influence of two or more independent variables (X) on the dependent variable (Y). The results of multiple linear testing using the help of SPSS 26, these results can be seen in the following table:

Table 1. Multiple Linear Regression Tests Coefficientsa

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	T	Itself.	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)		6.328	3.547		1.784	.079
	Self-efficacy	.294		.083	.323	3.530	.001
	Entrepreneurial Skills	.616		.091	.618	6.755	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Readiness of Entrepreneurial Students

Sumber: SPSS Output data 26, 2023

Multiple linear tests that have been carried out in research such as the results of SPSS 26 output in table 1 use the following equation:

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2$$

$$Y = 6.328 + 0.294 X_1 + 0.616 X_2$$

From the coefficient equation above, the description of table 4.6 is as follows:

- Is a constant situation when the variable of Student Readiness for Entrepreneurship is influenced by Self-Efficacy (X1) and Entrepreneurial Skills (X2). If the independent variable does not exist, the variable of student readiness for entrepreneurship does not exist.
- B1 (the value of the regression coefficient X1) of 0.294 shows that Self-Efficacy has a positive influence on Student Entrepreneurship Readiness which means that every 1% increase in the Self-Efficacy variable will affect the Entrepreneurial Student Readiness variable of 0.294.
- B2 (regression coefficient value X2) of 0.616 shows that the Entrepreneurial Skills variable has a positive influence on the Entrepreneurial Student Agility which means that every 1% increase in the Entrepreneurial Skills variable will affect the Entrepreneurial Student Readiness variable of 0.616.

The coefficient of determination (R squared) of the variables Self-efficacy and Entrepreneurial skills is 0.773. This shows that all independent variables (self-efficacy and entrepreneurial skills) simultaneously have an influence of 77.3% on the dependent variable (readiness of authoritative students). While the remaining 22.7% was influenced by other variables outside this study entrepreneurial ability, entrepreneurial behavior, creativity, innovation and hard work. Test t to determine the relationship of each independent variable individually to the dependent. To determine the effect of the independent variable on the dependent used a significant level of 5%. The decision-making criteria in this test are as follows:

- If the Sig value < 0.05, or $t_{\text{calculate}} > t_{\text{table}}$, there is no effect of variable X on variable Y.
- If the Sig value > 0.05, or $t_{\text{calculate}} < t_{\text{table}}$, then there is an influence of variable X on variable Y.

The results of the X1 variable t test using SPSS 26 can be seen in table 4.6 page 71 below:

Based on table 4.6 page 71 on the correlation test by knowing the rows, columns t and sig bias are explained as follows:

a. The Effect of Self-Efficacy Variables (X1) on Student Readiness for Entrepreneurship (Y)

The Self-Efficacy Variable (X1) has a positive and significant effect on Student Readiness for Entrepreneurship (Y), this is seen from the significant value of $0.001 < 0.05$. The value of $t_{table} = (a2: n-k-1 = (0.025:76-1) = (0.25:75) = 1.665$. This means that the calculated value is greater than the t_{table} value ($3,530 > 1,665$), then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, meaning that there is a significant influence of Self-Efficacy on Student Entrepreneurship Readiness.

b. The Effect of Entrepreneurial Skills (X2) variables on Student Entrepreneurship Readiness (Y)

The variable of Entrepreneurial Skills (X2) has a positive and significant effect on the Readiness of Entrepreneurial Students (Y), this is seen from the significant value of $0.000 < 0.05$. Value of $t_{table} = (a 2: n-k-1 = (0.025:76-1) = (0.25:75) = 1.665$. This means that the calculated t value is greater than the table t value ($6.755 > 1.665$), then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, meaning that there is a significant influence of Entrepreneurial Skills on Student Entrepreneurship Readiness.

The f test is used to determine whether all independent variables have an effect simultaneously on the dependent variable. According to Pramata and Permatasari (2021:45) the basis for decision making:

- a. If the Sig value < 0.05 , or $F_{calculate} > F_{table}$, there is a simultaneous influence of variable X on variable Y.
- b. If the Sig value > 0.05 , or $t_{calculate} < t_{table}$, there is no simultaneous effect of variable X on variable Y.

Table 2. Test F ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Itself.
1	Regression	3469.083	2	1734.541	170.065	.000b
	Residual	744.549	73	10.199		
	Total	4213.632	75			

a. Dependent Variable: Readiness of Entrepreneurial Students

b. Predictors: (Constant), Entrepreneurial Skills, Self-efficacy

Source: SPSS output data 26, 2023

Based on table 2, it can be known that the significance value for Self-Efficacy (X1) and Entrepreneurial Skills (X2) on Student Readiness for Entrepreneurship (Y) is a sig value of $0.000 < a$ significance level value of 0.05 and a calculation value of $170.065 > a$ f_{table} value of 3.127 . This means that H_0 is accepted and H_a is rejected. This means that there is a significant influence of Self-Efficacy (X1) and Entrepreneurial Skills (X2) variables on Student Entrepreneurship Readiness (Y).

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of research on the effect of self-efficacy and entrepreneurial skills on the readiness of entrepreneurial students in the era of society 5.0 at STKIP Persada Khatulistiwa Sintang. Then the results of the study can be made the following conclusions:

1. There is a partial influence of Self-Efficacy and Entrepreneurial Skills on the Readiness of Entrepreneurial Students of the Society 5.0 Era at STKIP Persada Khatulistiwa Sintang. This can be proven by the value of the t test which shows in the table t value of $3.530 > t_{table} 1.665$, meaning that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. Furthermore, there is the influence of Entrepreneurial Skills on the Readiness of Entrepreneurial Students in the Society 5.0 Era at STKIP Persada Khatulistiwa Sintang. This can be proven by a calculated t value of $6.755 > t_{table} 1.665$, meaning that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted
2. There is a simultaneous influence of Self-Efficacy on the Readiness of Entrepreneurial Students of the Society Era 5.0 at STKIP Persada Khatulistiwa Sintang. H_0 this can be proven by the F test value which shows the F_{table} value of $F_{calculate} 170.065 > F_{table} 3.127$. This means that H_0 is accepted and H_a is rejected, meaning that there is a significant influence of Self-Efficacy and Entrepreneurial Skills on the Readiness of Entrepreneurial Students in the Society 5.0 Era at STKIP Persada Khatulistiwa Sintang.
3. Based on the results of multiple linear regression, which has a dominant influence, the variable of Entrepreneurial Student Readiness (Y) is the variable of Entrepreneurial Skills X2 because it has a higher coefficient of 0.616 compared to the Self-Efficacy variable X1 with a coefficient value of 0.294.

FURTHER RESEARCH

This research still has limitations so further research needs to be done on this topic "The Influence of Self-Efficacy and Entrepreneurial Skills Towards the Readiness of Entrepreneurial Students in the Era of Society 5.0".

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